

Modelling electrochemical modulation of ion release in thin-layer samples

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ABSTRACT

In this work, we present a model based on the finite element approach to describe the electrochemically controlled release of ions from a redox-active film into a sample confined to a thin-layer spatial domain. The model includes the effect of interfacial charge transfer kinetics and 1D-diffusion treatment for an electron transfer-ion transfer (ET-IT) coupled reaction. More in detail, the oxidation of the redox-active film (ET) involves an ion release to an aqueous phase (IT). The dynamic concentration of the released ion is calculated when the ET-IT reaction proceeds under potentiostatic control, and the effect of the thickness of each phase (i.e., film or aqueous) on the diffusion profile is analyzed. The model is experimentally validated for the particular case in which oxidation of a thin film of polyaniline (PANI, 10 μm in thickness) is linked to the release of protons from the film into an electrolyte solution. The proton release produces certain pH changes in the electrolyte that are monitored by a pH sensor located at 330 μm from the PANI film. The charge associated with the proton release is related to the dynamic concentration of protons in the electrolyte through pH-coulograms that agree with the theoretical predictions. Overall, the model can reproduce the general behavior of the experimental proton pump and provides key insights into the functioning mechanism of electrochemical systems where redox and ion transfer reactions are coupled.

1. Introduction

Electrochemical sensors conceived on the basis of thin films coupled to thin-layer solution/sample have become a very attractive concept that benefits from robustness, fast mass transport, exhaustive conversion, reduction of both IR drop and capacitive issues, short conditioning, rapid equilibration, fast regeneration, and large capacity to be miniaturized in flat surfaces (e.g., paper-based electrodes, screen printed electrodes), among others [1–3]. One of the most prominent examples of this class of sensors is the pioneering work by Feldman and Heller that resulted in the well-known coulometry glucose finger prick assay [4]. Briefly, the electrochemical biosensor consisted of a very thin polymeric film where a glucose oxidase enzyme and an osmium redox mediator were entrapped and in contact with a confined and tiny compartment that receives the blood sample. The glucose is then exhaustively read due to the thin layer construction of the platform, and thus, a coulometry approach was possible [5]. This concept has also been considered in the development of other biosensors (e.g., fructose), though never reaching the maturity and well-entrenched technological state of the glucose sensor [6,7].

Beyond biosensing strategies, and focusing strictly on ion-transfer processes between two interfaces using thin-layer samples, Osakai

and Ortuno demonstrated that coulometry as a readout was feasible for ion determination [8,9]. The approach was further translated to the transport of ions between two solutions separated by a tubular perm-selective membrane (e.g., made of polypropylene, Nafion). For that purpose, a potential was applied to the working electrode, which was placed inside the tubular membrane, resulting in the net transport of the target ion from the sample (outside the membrane) to the inner solution. This formal evidence really transcended in the electrochemistry field because a linear relationship between charge and concentration was observed for many different ions, which paved the way towards interesting analytical applications. For example, simultaneous detection of halides in any water sample was demonstrated by promoting its gradual transfer from the sample to the working electrode, where they were electroplating at different potentials (i.e., in this order, chloride, bromide, and iodide) [10]. Heparin/protamine detection in human blood/serum was also possible in a similar arrangement [11].

Another interesting path recently explored in the literature is the use of thin-layer confinement not only for the direct quantification of ions but also as electrochemical ion pumps or sinks [12–19]. In this latter approach, an electrochemical pulse activates the release or uptake of ions from or towards a redox active film in a highly con-

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trolled manner. Given the reduced dimensions (mainly in terms of spatial thickness) of both the film and the sample, it is experimentally feasible to fully deplete/enrich the solution from/of a particular ion [20], providing a plausible approach towards calibration-free sensors [21,22]. Note that, from the analytical point of view, electrochemical ion pumps have mainly been investigated in the acidification of well-confined microliter-sized water samples ($<100 \mu\text{L}$) [14,23–25]. Ion-selective membranes (ISM) doped with hydrogen ionophores have been used as proton pumps for the ultimate determination of alkalinity in artificial and natural water samples [26]. A more robust alternative was also explored by replacing the ISM for a thin film ($<100 \mu\text{m}$) of polyaniline (PANI), which was demonstrated to release protons upon activation with a constant potential [25].

Regardless of the physicochemical nature of the film acting as the proton pump (ion-selective membrane or conducting polymer), their use under potentiostatic conditions for the acidification of aqueous samples provides pH-charge curves (also referred to as pH-coulograms), where the pH change in the sample/solution upon proton release is monitored. The procedure is similar to a traditional volumetric titration but at a miniaturized scale and requiring a shorter analysis time [13]. Indeed, the idea could also be applied to other ions rather than protons. The main difference compared to a volumetric titration is that this latter works under hydrodynamic conditions, in contrast to thin-layer ion pumps that work under static regimes: diffusion of ions in both the thin-layer pump and the aqueous sample can have a significant effect on the measured analytical signal. In addition, the kinetics of the ion transfer (IT) process from the pump to the aqueous (sample) phase must be considered in experimental conditions in which the ion pump works at low overpotentials, and hence the IT process is not completely controlled by diffusion.

Different mathematical models have been elaborated to describe the dynamic charge transfer phenomenon in thin layer materials [27–29]. From early models, which aimed to understand electron transfer (ET) between metal electrodes and thin-layer solutions [30,31], through the mathematical treatment of the thin-film mercury electrode [32,33] to the treatment of IT(s) in ion-selective membranes [28,34,35]. The complexity of these theoretical definitions varies from relatively simple approaches that neglect diffusion or migration to more elaborate models where the Nernst-Planck equation is solved [27,29]. Nevertheless, as far as we know, there is not yet a model which links the behavior of thin-layer electrochemistry with ion transfer from redox active films.

We aim to understand the role of IT kinetics and diffusion in the functioning mechanism of thin-layer ion pumps; therefore, we present herein a model based on the finite element approach to describe electrochemically controlled ion release from a redox active thin film into an aqueous sample confined to a micrometer spatial domain. The ion release is modeled as a two-step process in which a redox reaction in the thin film is coupled (and indeed overlaps) with an ion flux from the film to the sample. The model considers Butler-Volmer kinetics of each charge transfer step (ET and IT) and 1D-diffusion mass transport to calculate the dependence of the ion concentration in the aqueous sample with time and distance from the film, as well as the electrical charge that is associated to the ion release (i.e., ion transfer charge). Unlike other theoretical approaches to coupled ET–IT reactions, the model presented herein does not assume equilibrium conditions for neither the ET nor the IT step [36–38]. Thus, the rate for the overall ET–IT charge transfer process is considered to be dependent on both, the overpotential of the ET step between the redox film and conductive substrate, and the overpotential of the IT step between the film and the aqueous sample.

First, we present the mathematical theory and analyze the behavior of a general thin-layer ion pump in terms of concentration of the transferring ion in both phases (i.e., the ion pump and aqueous phase) and the current that represents the rate of the ion release from the ion pump to the aqueous phase (solution). Subsequently, to validate the

theoretical model, we investigate the experimental behavior of a thin film (ca. $10\text{-}\mu\text{m}$ thickness) of polyaniline (PANI) in contact with an aqueous electrolyte solution confined to a $330\mu\text{m}$ thick space. Upon oxidation, the PANI thin film acts as a proton pump via protons' release into the solution. Then, the protons diffuse away from the pump surface towards a pH sensor electrode located opposite to the pump. The pH sensor presents a fast response time and provides the proton concentration (pH) at its local vicinity. The validation is accomplished by comparing the experimental and calculated pH-coulograms (pH at the sensor versus ion transfer charge) in neutral pH (e.g., 100 mM NaCl) and basic (e.g., 1 mM Na_2CO_3) electrolyte solutions. A satisfactory agreement was observed, with the model successfully describing dynamic change in the pH of the aqueous phase as a function of the IT charge. The model also gives an insight into the effect of the thickness of the ion pump and the aqueous layer on the experimental pH-coulogram, with pH-coulograms converging to volumetric titration curves for thickness values close to $100\mu\text{m}$.

2. Theory

Figure 1 illustrates a schematic representation of the system under study, which is composed of a conductive substrate homogeneously covered with a redox-active film (interface 1) and jointly comprising the working electrode (WE). The WE is in contact with an aqueous phase ideally confined into a thin-layer spatial domain (interface 2) and it is connected to a reference electrode (RE) and counter electrode (CE) that are immersed in the aqueous phase. A potential difference (E_{app}) is applied between the WE and the RE for a particular time (t). This potential generates an ET process at the interface 1 that causes the oxidization of the redox-active film (M), from its reduced (M^{red}) to its oxidized form (M^{ox}). The ET is additionally coupled to an IT step defined as a cation release (I^+) from the film M to the aqueous solution through the interface 2. Accordingly, the application of the external potential provokes two interconnected charge transfer steps (i.e., ET at the interface 1 and IT at the interface 2) that are manifested in the current output (i_{Total}) for the overall process.

To consider all types of ET and IT kinetics, from completely irreversible to completely reversible processes, the dependence of the charge transfer rate on the potential difference at each interface is described using Butler-Volmer kinetics. In this way, the model can be used on experimental systems containing not reversible redox mediators (such as conducting polymers upon an applied potential) and considering IT reactions that are kinetically limited [39–43]. Accordingly, the ET (Oxidation) step is described as follows:

$$k_{ET} = k_{ET}^0 \exp\left[\frac{1}{2} \frac{F\eta_{ET}}{RT}\right] \quad (2)$$

where the transfer coefficient (α) was taken as $1/2$, k_{ET}^0 and k_{ET} are the standard and kinetic rate constants for the ET step respectively, F and R the faraday and gas constants, T the temperature, and η_{ET} the overpotential for ET. The latter is defined as $E_{ET} - E_{ET}^0$, with E_{ET} as the potential at the interface 1 and E_{ET}^0 as the standard redox potential of M .

Analogously, the IT (related to the ion release) step is defined as follows:

$$k_{IT} = k_{IT}^0 \exp\left[\frac{F\eta_{IT}}{2RT}\right] \quad (4)$$

where 'film' and 'aq' denote the redox active film "M" and the aqueous phase respectively, I_{film}^+ and I_{aq}^+ are the ion I^+ in the film and aqueous phases, k_{IT}^0 and k_{IT} the standard and kinetic rate constants for the IT step

Fig. 1. a) Schematic representation of the electrochemical system studied in this work. WE = working electrode, RE = reference electrode, CE = counter electrode, E_{app} = applied potential, i_{total} = total experimental current. b) Spatial domain. δ_{film} = thickness of the film. δ_{aq} = thickness of the aqueous phase. x_{max} = thickness of the total domain.

respectively, and η_{IT} the overpotential for IT. The latter is defined as $(\Delta\phi - \Delta\phi_{I^+}^0)$, with $\Delta\phi$ as the Galvani potential difference at the interface 2, and $\Delta\phi_{I^+}^0$ the standard redox potential for the transfer of I^+ from the film “M” to the aqueous phase.

By combining the two charge transfer steps, the following overall reaction is obtained:

with the total kinetic constant (k_{total}) expressed as a combination of the ET and IT constants (Equation (6)), in a similar way to other heterogeneous ET–IT coupled reactions (e.g., electrochemical concerted proton electron transfer) [44].

$$k_{total} = k_{ET-IT}^0 \exp\left[\frac{\alpha F \eta_{total}}{RT}\right] \quad (6)$$

The total overpotential (η_{total}) and its relationship with the applied potential (E_{app}) is defined by **Equations (7)–(10)** [45,46]:

$$\eta_{total} = \eta_{ET} + \eta_{IT} \quad (7)$$

$$E_{app} = E_{ET} + \Delta\phi \quad (8)$$

$$\eta_{total} = (E_{ET} - E^0) + (\Delta\phi - \Delta\phi_{I^+}^0) \quad (9)$$

$$\eta_{total} = E_{app} - (E^0 + \Delta\phi_{I^+}^0) \quad (10)$$

with equations (6) and (7) formulated to group the contribution of both charge transfer steps to the overall ET–IT kinetics. An in-depth discussion regarding the chemical nature of η_{total} and k_{total} is not considered in this work: Numerical values for each term are used in the simulations (*vide infra*). Notably, the consideration of the coupling nature of the ET–IT, and so the validity of the equations (6) and (7), is reinforced by recent results in the field. Essentially, an spectroelectrochemistry approach have been developed to obtain the first empirical evidence that ET occurs in conducting polymers—in particular poly(3-octylthiophene)—only when the associated IT ensuring the system electroneutrality is energetically available [47,48].

Considering the diffusion terms for each species (M^{Red} , M^{Ox} , I_{film}^+ , I_{aq}^+), the dependence of the concentrations on the distance (x) and time (t) domains, and neglecting migration effects within each phase, the overall kinetics of the ET–IT process can be described by a series of coupled partial differential equations (PDEs) at each interface as follows:

Region 1: PDEs for the redox active film (ET step). Equations (11) and (12) are the diffusion differential equations with spatial domain $0 \leq x \leq \delta_{film}$.

$$\frac{\partial c_{M^{Red}}(x, t)}{\partial t} = D_{M^{Red}} \nabla^2 c_{M^{Red}}(x, t) \quad (11)$$

$$\frac{\partial c_{M^{Ox}}(x, t)}{\partial t} = D_{M^{Ox}} \nabla^2 c_{M^{Ox}}(x, t) \quad (12)$$

The initial condition assumes that only M^{Red} is initially present in the film:

$$c_{M^{Ox}}(x, 0) = 0 \quad (13)$$

$$c_{M^{Red}} = [M^{Red}]_{Bulk} \quad (14)$$

For the boundary condition, the fluxes of the oxidized and reduced species at the interface 1 are set according to a first-order rate law for an interfacial process [49]:

$$D_{M^{Red}} \left(\frac{-\partial c_{M^{Red}}}{\partial x} \right)_{x=interface1} = D_{M^{Ox}} \left(\frac{\partial c_{M^{Ox}}}{\partial x} \right)_{x=interface1} = k_{total} (c_{M^{Red}})_{x=interface1} \quad (15)$$

with the oxidation current ($i_{Oxidation}$) defined as:

$$i_{Oxidation} = FA_1 D_{M^{Ox}} \left(\frac{\partial c_{M^{Ox}}}{\partial x} \right)_{x=interface1} \quad (16)$$

and the oxidation charge ($Q_{Oxidation}$) defined as:

$$Q_{Oxidation} = \int_0^{tmax} i_{Oxidation} dt \quad (17)$$

Regions 1 and 2: PDEs for IT step. Equations (18) and (19) are the diffusion differential equations with a spatial domain $0 \leq x \leq \delta_{film}$ and $\delta_{film} \leq x \leq x_{max}$ respectively.

$$\frac{\partial c_{I_{film}^+}(x, t)}{\partial t} = D_{I_{film}^+} \nabla^2 c_{I_{film}^+}(x, t) \quad (18)$$

$$\frac{\partial c_{I_{aq}^+}(x, t)}{\partial t} = D_{I_{aq}^+} \nabla^2 c_{I_{aq}^+}(x, t) \quad (19)$$

The initial condition assumes that only I_{film}^+ is initially present in the film:

$$c_{I_{aq}^+}(x, 0) = 0 \quad (20)$$

$$c_{I_{film}^+} = [I_{film}^+]_{Bulk} \quad (21)$$

For the boundary condition, the flux of I^+ at the interface 2 is expressed according to a first-order rate law for an interfacial process as

$$D_{film}^+ \left(\frac{-\partial C_{film}^+}{\partial x} \right)_{x=interface2} = D_{aq}^+ \left(\frac{\partial C_{aq}^+}{\partial x} \right)_{x=interface2} = k_{total} (C_{film}^+)_{x=interface2} \quad (22)$$

with the IT current (i_{IT}) defined as

$$i_{IT} = FA_2 D_{aq}^+ \left(\frac{\partial C_{aq}^+}{\partial x} \right)_{x=interface2} \quad (23)$$

and the IT charge (Q_{IT}) defined as

$$Q_{IT} = \int_0^{t_{max}} i_{IT} dt \quad (24)$$

and where δ_{film} , δ_{aq} and x_{max} denote the thickness of the redox active film, the aqueous phase and the total spatial domain respectively, D and c the diffusion coefficient and concentration terms of each species, A_1 and A_2 the surface areas of interfaces 1 and 2, $[M^{Red}]_{Bulk}$ and $[I_{film}^+]_{Bulk}$ the initial bulk concentrations, and ∇^2 the Laplacian operator.

Finally, considering the ET-IT coupling and electroneutrality conditions in the film, the relationship between the overall current and the current for each charge transfer step is denoted as:

$$i_{total} = i_{oxidation} = i_{IT} \quad (25)$$

In this way, the time and distance dependent concentration of I_{film}^+ and I_{aq}^+ can be calculated only considering the IT step at the interface 2 (Equations (18)–(22)), with k_{total} accounting for the ET-IT coupling.

3. Experimental section

3.1. Numerical simulations

The PDE system was solved numerically using the method of lines [50], where only the spatial domain is discretized and the PDEs are converted into a system of time-dependent ordinary differential equations (ODEs) that are solved by integration. By discretizing only the space domain, instabilities and oscillations arising from an inappropriate selection of time and distance steps are minimized [51]. The spatial discretization was carried out using finite elements with a defined variable spatial step (Δx). A convergent solution was obtained using an asymmetric mesh centered at the membrane interface (Fig. S1 in the Supporting Information). The Δx value was selected to be adjustable and to decrease at the film/solution interface (interface 2) where the concentration gradients change rapidly.

Dimensionless parameters were used during all the simulations. The main parameters are presented in Equations (26)–(29), with Table S1 in the Supporting information containing a complete list of all the dimensionless parameters used and their relationship with real parameters.

$$\text{Diffusion : } D^* = D_{film}^+ / D_{aq}^+ \quad (26)$$

$$\text{Distance : } x^* = \delta_{aq} / \left(D_{aq}^+ \tau \right)^{1/2} \quad (27)$$

$$\text{Time : } t^* = t_{exp} / \tau \quad (28)$$

$$\text{Applied Potential : } E_{app}^* = (F/RT) \eta_{total} \quad (29)$$

For the dimensionless distance (x^*) and time (t^*), δ_{aq} denotes the thickness of the aqueous phase, t_{exp} the experimental time, and τ the time for the diffusion layer of I_{aq}^+ to reach the outer boundary of the aqueous phase, which is defined by Equation (30) [52].

$$\tau = \delta_{aq}^2 / D_{aq}^+ \quad (30)$$

All the PDEs were rewritten in dimensionless form and solved using the NDSolve function of the software Wolfram Mathematica 12.2, with the initial and boundary conditions presented in dimensionless form in

the Supporting information (Equations S1–S27). The interface 2 was introduced into the spatial domain as a region of finite thickness (100 times thinner than the film phase) and the IT step was modelled as a chemical reaction using spatial-dependent coefficients, as described in detail in the Supporting information (Section S.1.3) and Fig. S2. Whether only simulated values were analyzed or a comparison between simulated and experimental values was considered, the PDEs were first solved in dimensionless form, and the solution was transformed to real parameters using the relationships presented in Table S1 in the Supporting Information.

3.2. Experimental measurements

The proton pump and pH sensor were prepared via PANI electropolymerization on screen-printed electrodes (DRP-150 for the proton pump and DRP-250AT for the pH sensor, Metrohm Nordic AB). The electrodes were implemented into a 3D-printed microfluidic cell that was fabricated as described elsewhere [25]. Briefly, the cell comprises two electrode holders that allow placing the proton pump and the pH sensor electrodes in a face to face configuration and with the sample in between them through a microfluidic channel. The channel and sample volume ($330 \mu\text{m} \times 8 \text{mm}$) are defined by a spacer made from mylar sheets (RS components, Sweden) and adhesive transfer tape (3 M 9471LE, thickness of 0.058 mm), which were cut to the required shape using a Silhouette Cameo Cutter (USA). The counter electrode was located 1 mm far from the proton pump and 1 mm from the pH sensor (Fig. S3), and hence, any possible products generated at the counter electrode are not expected to influence the pH readout in the samples (i.e., in case of the generation of hydroxyl ions in the charge balancing reaction). To allow the exchange of samples in the microfluidic cell, this additionally contained an inlet and outlet for the flow of the sample solution through the spacer that defines the microchannel using an ISMATIC pump (flow rate of $100 \mu\text{L min}^{-1}$). The electrode acting as the pH sensor was connected to a potentiometer (Lawson labs EMF16 Interface, Lawson Laboratories, Inc.), and the proton pump was connected to a potentiostat (PGSTAT204 Autolab potentiostat, Metrohm Nordic AB). Once the sample is introduced into the cell (between the two PANI electrodes), the flow was stopped, and a constant potential pulse of 0.4 V was applied to the proton pump for 300 s, while the pH sensor continuously registered the pH in the sample.

4. Results and discussion

4.1. General behavior of an ion-pump thin-layer material.

The system is first defined under symmetrical conditions, with the redox active film and aqueous phases considered with equal thicknesses. The total spatial domain spans from $x^* = 0$ to $x^* = 4$. Thus, the interface 2 is located at $x^* = 2$, with the film located within the interval of $0 \leq x^* < 2$ and the aqueous phase within the interval of $2 < x^* \leq 4$. In addition, the diffusion coefficient ratio (D_{film}^+ / D_{aq}^+) was assumed to be equal to 1. Under these considerations, Fig. 2 shows the concentration profiles obtained from the numerical solution of Equations (18) and (19) at different times during the transfer of I^+ from the film to the aqueous phase (i.e., at the interface 2). The profiles revealed that, at $t^* = 0$ (i.e., open circuit potential, OCP), I^+ is present only in the film, with the interface at $x^* = 2$ acting as an energy barrier that hinders the IT step (Fig. 2a). After applying an overpotential of $E_{app} = 0.4 \text{V}$, the IT from the film to the aqueous phase occurs, and hence, an increase in the dimensionless concentration of I_{aq}^+ (C_{aq}^+) is predicted (Fig. 2b–d). Given the symmetry of the system, equal diffusion layers are developed on each side of the interface 2. In case of the aqueous phase and at longer times, the diffusion layer grows until it reaches the outer boundary of the spatial domain (Fig. 2c). Finally,

Fig. 2. Dimensionless concentration profiles for I_{film}^{+} (c_{film}^{+}) and I_{aq}^{+} (c_{aq}^{+}) at different times after applying an overpotential of $E_{app}^{*} = 11.7$ (equivalent to E_{app} 0.4 V): (a) $t^{*} = 0$, (b) $t^{*} = 0.02$, (c) $t^{*} = 0.7$ and (d) $t^{*} = 10$ (2τ). Kinetic parameter $\lambda^0 = 3.3$. $D^{*} = 1$. A complete definition of all the dimensionless parameters and the values used during the simulation are presented in the Supporting Information.

at $t^{*} = 2\tau$, all I_m^{+} has been transferred to the aqueous phase, with $c_{film}^{+} = 0$ and $c_{aq}^{+} = 1$ (Fig. 2d).

From the concentration at the interface 2 ($x^{*} = 2$), the dimensionless fluxes of I_m^{+} ($\psi_{I_m^{+}}$) and I_{aq}^{+} ($\psi_{I_{aq}^{+}}$) were calculated using Equations (31) and (32) and are presented in Fig. 3. As observed, the calculated

fluxes at the interface satisfied the boundary conditions introduced in Equation (22), considering $\psi_{I_{aq}^{+}} = -\psi_{I_m^{+}}$ (Fig. 3a) with an estimated error of 5.6 % (Fig. S4).

$$\psi_{I_{film}^{+}}(t^{*}) = D^{*} \frac{\partial c_{film}^{+}(x^{*}, t^{*})}{\partial x^{*}} \Big|_{x^{*}=2} \quad (31)$$

$$\psi_{I_{aq}^{+}}(t^{*}) = -D^{*} \frac{\partial c_{aq}^{+}(x^{*}, t^{*})}{\partial x^{*}} \Big|_{x^{*}=2} \quad (32)$$

Additionally, the dimensionless flux is in direct proportion to the current and the overall rate of the charge transfer in the system. The flux dependence on $(t^{*})^{-1/2}$ (Fig. 3b) and its convergence to a Cottrellian slope (Fig. S5) showed that, at short times, the rate of IT is primarily controlled by diffusion mass transfer until the diffusion layer reaches the outer boundary of the distance domain. At this point (ca., $t^{*} = 0.5$), the flux deviates from the linearity predicted by the pure Cottrellian diffusion model [53] until a zero flux is obtained at long times, with all the I_{film}^{+} transferred to the aqueous phase. Importantly, the described effect for the outer boundary indicates that, at the selected conditions, the system behaves under a thin-layer diffusion regime [49,54].

The effect of the thickness of each phase on the I^{+} concentration profiles was investigated, and the corresponding simulations are shown in Fig. 4. Two cases were analyzed: (i) the M film was 20 times thinner than the aqueous phase (Fig. 4a), and (ii) the M film was 20 times thicker than the aqueous phase (Fig. 4b). In both cases, the asymmetry of the system was reflected in different diffusion regimes at each side of interface 2, with nearly flat concentration profiles in the thinner phase and a growing diffusion layer in the thicker one. The presence of two different diffusional regimes highlights the role of the phase thickness in the mass transport behavior. Indeed, the presence of flat concentration profiles in the thinner phase is associated with an increase in diffusional mass transport.

According to the theory of diffusion in thin layer domains, the mentioned increase in the diffusional mass transport can be calculated as

Fig. 3. Flux of I_{film}^{+} and I_{aq}^{+} at the interface 2 as a function of (a) t^{*} and (b) $(t^{*})^{-1/2}$. Overpotential of $E_{app}^{*} = 11.7$ (equivalent to E_{app} 0.4 V). Kinetic parameter $\lambda^0 = 0.9$. $D^{*} = 1$.

Fig. 4. Concentration profiles for I_{film}^+ (left axis) and I_{aq}^+ (right axis) at different times for (a) $\delta_{\text{film}}/\delta_{\text{aq}} = 1/20$ and (b) $\delta_{\text{film}}/\delta_{\text{aq}} = 20$. $E_{\text{app}}^* = 11.7$ (equivalent to $E_{\text{app}} 0.4$ V). Kinetic parameter $\lambda^0 = 0.9$. $D^* = 1$. The interface 2 is located at $x^* = 0.1$ in (a) and $x^* = 2$ in (b). A complete definition of all the dimensionless parameters and the values used during the simulation are presented in the Supporting Information.

the rate constant for a planar diffusion event (k_{diff}), which has the form of $D/(\delta_{\text{film}})^2$, with D as the diffusion coefficient and δ_{film} as the thickness of the film [55]. A simple calculation using this equation reveals that, by decreasing the thickness of the film 10 times, k_{diff} can be increased by 2 orders of magnitude. To put this effect in context, decreasing 10 times the thickness of the film has the same effect on k_{diff} as an increase of 120 mV on the interfacial IT constant k_{IT} (Equation (4)). In addition, it is worth noting that the concentration profiles obtained for the transfer of I^+ from a thin-film of M to a thick aqueous phase (Fig. 4a) are in agreement with the profiles obtained analytically for the oxidation of a thin-film mercury electrode under diffusion control [32], and with the interfacial mass transport of enzymes in thin layers [56]. The similarity between these results suggests that the numerical model herein presented can successfully describe interfacial mass transport of charged species under diffusion control, in cases where the analyte of interest is confined into a thin-layer spatial domain.

4.2. The particular case of a thin film of PANI acting as proton pump

To validate the model, and to gain a fundamental understanding of the functioning of a real thin-layer electrochemical system, we analyzed the case of a thin film of PANI acting as an electrochemical proton pump. Three main assumptions were made in this analysis: (i) upon oxidation, the conductivity of the PANI film was sufficiently large to neglect migration effects; (ii) charge compensation in the film proceeds only through the release of protons into the aqueous film; and (iii) the redox behavior of the polymer was controlled by the transport of counterions and not by electron hopping within the film. These assumptions were made based on experimental observations that revealed that the conductivity of PANI increases four orders of magnitude upon oxidation [57], and the difficulty of quantifying the contri-

bution of different ions (such as Cl^-) to charge compensation due to the complex nature of this process [58]. In this way, the PANI film was treated as an example of a redox active material where ET and IT steps are coupled, and where the overall rate of charge transfer is only controlled by interfacial kinetics and diffusional mass transport [59–61].

The experimental system is illustrated in Fig. 5. A PANI thin film ($\delta_{\text{film}} = 10 \mu\text{m}$) is in contact with an aqueous electrolyte solution confined into a spatial domain of a defined thickness (δ_{aq}). As previously demonstrated in our group [25], upon oxidation, the PANI film releases protons into the aqueous electrolyte. Then, the protons diffuse away from the film towards a pH sensor located at a distance equal to δ_{aq} . The validation of the model is performed by comparing the experimental and simulated pH profiles as a function of the electrochemical charge associated to the proton release (pH-coulograms). The pH profiles are calculated and experimentally obtained (as described in the experimental section) in two different solutions: 100 mM NaCl and 1 mM Na_2CO_3 . As illustrated in Fig. 5, the main difference between these two solutions is that in the Na_2CO_3 content, and thus, an additional chemical reaction between the protons released from the pump and CO_3^{2-} takes place in the aqueous phase. This reaction affects not only to the diffusion regimes but also the pH readout provided by the sensor.

4.2.1. Proton release in NaCl solution

The first experimental case that was analyzed consisted of a thin film of PANI in contact with a neutral electrolyte (100 mM NaCl solution). Upon oxidation, the film produces protons that are transferred to the aqueous phase according to Equations (33) and (34) for the ET and IT steps respectively:

a) NaCl SOLUTION

a) Na_2CO_3 SOLUTION

Fig. 5. Schematic representation of the experimental proton pump system used to validate the model presented in this work: a) aqueous phase = NaCl, and b) aqueous phase = Na_2CO_3 .

where $[PANI - H]^{Red^0}$ and $[PANI - H]^{Ox^+}$ denote the PANI film in its reduced and oxidized state respectively, and H_{PANI}^+ and H_{aq}^+ denote the protons in the film and the aqueous phase respectively.

To maintain the electroneutrality in the film, the rate of both events must be equal. Therefore, the kinetics of the total process (ET-IT) can be described only in terms of the IT as presented in **Equation (35)**:

with k_{total} being the total ET-IT rate constant, as defined in **Equation (6)**.

The concentrations of H_{PANI}^+ and H_{aq}^+ ($c_{H_{PANI}^+}$ and $c_{H_{aq}^+}$) were calculated by solving **Equations (18) and (19)**, considering that $H_{PANI}^+ = I_m^+$ and $H_{aq}^+ = I_{aq}^+$ (**Fig. S6**). The pH readout was calculated from the time dependent concentration of H_{aq}^+ as $-\log c_{H_{aq}^+}(x = \delta_{aq}, t)$. The total current and charge associated with the oxidation of the film and the coupled IT event were calculated using **Equations (16), (17), (23) and (24)**, considering a 1:1 stoichiometric ratio between the oxidation of PANI and the transfer of H_{PANI}^+ (**Equations (33) and (34)**) and with $Q_{Oxidation} = Q_{IT}$.

Figure 6a presents the pH profiles obtained experimentally ($pH_{Sensor-experimental}$, blue line) and simulated ($pH_{Sensor-simulated}$, black line) as a function of the experimental oxidation charge ($Q_{Oxidation}^{Experimental}$ obtained from the data in **Fig. S7**) and the simulated ion transfer charge ($Q_{IT}^{Simulated}$ calculated using **Equations 24 and S28-S31**). A comparison between the two profiles shows that the model reproduces the pH at the sensor with a maximum difference of 0.25 pH units between the experimental and simulated pH (**Fig. 6a and Fig. S8**). Furthermore, in both cases (experimental and simulated), the pH profile can be divided into a diffusional period where the pH readout is constant, and a sensing period where the pH provided by the sensor changes according to the concentration of H^+ released to the aqueous phase.

As observed in **Fig. 6b**, the diffusional period corresponds to the charge consumed before the concentration of H_{aq}^+ increases at a distance $x = \delta_{aq}$. In terms of time, the diffusional period is associated with the time necessary for H_{aq}^+ to diffuse from the pump to the sensor surface (**Fig. S9**). Thus, in absence of other types of mass transport phenomena (such as migration or convection), the diffusional period is only dependent on the diffusion coefficient of protons in the aqueous phase and the distance between the proton pump and the sensor (i.e., δ_{aq}). This was further confirmed in the results shown in **Fig. 6c**, where a comparison of simulated pH-coulograms (pH at the sensor versus $Q_{IT}^{Simulated}$) for different values of δ_{aq} revealed that the diffusional period is shorter as the aqueous phase thickness decreases. In addition, the agreement observed between $Q_{Oxidation}^{Experimental}$ and $Q_{IT}^{Simulated}$ confirmed that, under the experimental conditions presented in this work, **Equation (25)** can be successfully applied and the kinetics of the coupled ET-IT reaction can be described by considering only one of the charge transfer steps (ET or IT).

4.2.2. Proton release in Na_2CO_3 solution

The electrochemically controlled transfer of protons from the PANI film was next coupled with to acid-base reaction in the aqueous phase, i.e., the neutralization of Na_2CO_3 . In this case, the model can be easily modified to consider the chemical reaction by defining the overall reaction kinetics in terms of a two-step ion transfer chemical reaction mechanism (IC), as presented in **Equations (36) and (37)**.

Fig. 6. Profiles for pH and concentration of H_{aq}^+ at the sensor surface as a function of charge. **(a)** Simulated and experimental pH-coulograms for a 330 μm aqueous phase (δ_{aq}). **(b)** Calculated concentration of H_{aq}^+ at the sensor surface as a function of time and simulated charge for $\delta_{aq} = 330 \mu\text{m}$. **(c)** Simulated pH-coulograms for different thickness of the aqueous phase. The experimental data was obtained for the oxidation of a PANI thin layer at 0.4 V for 120 s in presence of 100 mM NaCl. All the parameters used to obtain the simulated data are presented in the Supporting Information.

The chemical reaction is formally introduced into the model by adding PDEs for CO_3^{2-} and HCO_3^- species and a chemical reaction term in the PDE for H_{aq}^+ (**Equations (38)–(41)**). After solving the PDE system and calculating the dynamic concentrations of H_{PANI}^+ , H_{aq}^+ , CO_3^{2-} and HCO_3^- (**Figs. S10–S12**), the pH provided by the sensor was calcu-

lated by solving a fourth-degree polynomial obtained from mass balances and acid-base equilibria of CO_3^{2-} (Equations S32–S46 in the Supporting Information). More in detail:

PDEs for IT in the presence of a chemical reaction. Equation (37) is the diffusion differential equation with spatial domain $0 \leq x \leq \delta_{\text{film}}$

$$\frac{\partial c_{H_{\text{PANI}}^+}(x, t)}{\partial t} = D_{H_{\text{PANI}}^+} \nabla^2 c_{H_{\text{PANI}}^+}(x, t) \quad (38)$$

Equations (39)–(41) are the diffusion differential equations with spatial domain $\delta_{\text{film}} \leq x \leq \delta_{\text{aq}}$.

$$\frac{\partial c_{H_{\text{aq}}^+}(x, t)}{\partial t} = D_{H_{\text{aq}}^+} \nabla^2 c_{H_{\text{aq}}^+}(x, t) - k_1 [c_{H_{\text{aq}}^+}(x, t) c_{\text{CO}_3^{2-}}(x, t)] - k_2 [c_{H_{\text{aq}}^+}(x, t) c_{\text{HCO}_3^-}(x, t)] \quad (39)$$

$$\frac{\partial c_{\text{CO}_3^{2-}}(x, t)}{\partial t} = D_{\text{CO}_3^{2-}} \nabla^2 c_{\text{CO}_3^{2-}}(x, t) - k_1 [c_{H_{\text{aq}}^+}(x, t) c_{\text{CO}_3^{2-}}(x, t)] \quad (40)$$

$$\frac{\partial c_{\text{HCO}_3^-}(x, t)}{\partial t} = D_{\text{HCO}_3^-} \nabla^2 c_{\text{HCO}_3^-}(x, t) + k_1 [c_{H_{\text{aq}}^+}(x, t) c_{\text{CO}_3^{2-}}(x, t)] - k_2 [c_{H_{\text{aq}}^+}(x, t) c_{\text{HCO}_3^-}(x, t)] \quad (41)$$

It is assumed that only H_{PANI}^+ and CO_3^{2-} are initially present in the film and the aqueous phase respectively, and thus, the following initial conditions are presented:

For H_{PANI}^+ and H_{aq}^+ , Equations (20) and (21) were used considering that $H_{\text{PANI}}^+ = I_{\text{film}}^+$ and $H_{\text{aq}}^+ = I_{\text{aq}}^+$. Then, for CO_3^{2-} and HCO_3^- , the following equations were used:

$$c_{\text{CO}_3^{2-}} = [\text{CO}_3^{2-}]_{\text{bulk}} \quad (42)$$

$$c_{\text{HCO}_3^-} = 0 \quad (43)$$

Regarding the boundary conditions, for H_{PANI}^+ and H_{aq}^+ , Equation (22) was used considering that $H_{\text{PANI}}^+ = I_{\text{film}}^+$ and $H_{\text{aq}}^+ = I_{\text{aq}}^+$

For CO_3^{2-} and HCO_3^- , the following equation is introduced:

$$\begin{aligned} D_{\text{CO}_3^{2-}} \left(\frac{\partial c_{\text{CO}_3^{2-}}}{\partial x} \right)_{x=\text{interface2}} &= D_{\text{HCO}_3^-} \left(\frac{\partial c_{\text{HCO}_3^-}}{\partial x} \right)_{x=\text{interface2}} \\ &= D_{\text{CO}_3^{2-}} \left(\frac{\partial c_{\text{CO}_3^{2-}}}{\partial x} \right)_{x=x_{\text{max}}} \\ &= D_{\text{HCO}_3^-} \left(\frac{\partial c_{\text{HCO}_3^-}}{\partial x} \right)_{x=x_{\text{max}}} = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (44)$$

Figure 7 presents the pH profiles obtained via experiments ($\text{pH}_{\text{Sensor-experimental}}$, blue line) and simulation ($\text{pH}_{\text{Sensor-simulated}}$, black line) as a function of experimental oxidation charge ($Q_{\text{Oxidation}}^{\text{Experimental}}$, obtained from the data in Fig. S13) and simulated ion transfer charge ($Q_{\text{IT}}^{\text{Simulated}}$ calculated using Equation (24)). As observed, the general behavior of the pH is successfully reproduced by the model with a maximum difference of 0.6 units of pH between the experimental and simulated pH (Fig. 7a). Notably, the differences observed between the two profiles are mainly attributed to the simplification of the 3D diffusional regime in the real experiment to a unidimensional regime used in the model. Then, in both cases (experimental and simulated), the pH profile presents a diffusional period where the pH at the sensor is constant, followed by a pH drop. In the simulated profile, this drop is clearly observed to take place in two steps. The first step, observed at 3 mC, corresponds to a pH change associated with a decrease in the concentration of CO_3^{2-} in the sample, which is converted to HCO_3^- . The second step, observed at 6.5 mC, corresponds to an increase in the concentration of H_{aq}^+ that diffused from the PANI film (Fig. 7b, Figs. S14 and S15). In the experimental profile, the first pH decrease is observed at 5 mC, and the second decrease at 6.5 mC. A comparison

Fig. 7. Profiles for pH and concentration of H_{aq}^+ at the sensor surface as a function of charge. (a) Simulated and experimental pH-coulougrams for a 330 μm thickness of the aqueous phase (δ_{aq}). (b) Calculated concentration of H_{aq}^+ at the sensor as a function of time and simulated charge. (c) Simulated pH-coulougrams for different dimensions of the aqueous phase. The experimental data was obtained after oxidation of a PANI thin layer at 0.4 V for 120 s in presence of 1 mM of Na_2CO_3 . All the parameters used to obtain the simulated data are presented in the Supporting Information.

between Figs. 6b and 7b shows that Na_2CO_3 acts as a sort of chemical conversion barrier in which H_{aq}^+ first reacts with CO_3^{2-} before diffusing freely towards the sensor.

One of the most interesting results obtained experimentally, and indeed confirmed by the simulations, is the similarity between the pH-coulougrams observed with the proton pump and classical volumetric acid-base titration curves. A comparison between the two techniques showed that, in the case of the proton pump, the oxidation

charge acts similarly to the volume of titrant that is delivered in volumetric acid-base titrations. The main difference between the techniques is that, unlike volumetric titrations, the electrochemical proton pump may be a calibration-free methodology under some specific constraints [21]. Indeed, by knowing only the oxidation charge, the number of H^+ transferred to the electrolyte, and therefore the concentration of the unknown analyte, can be easily calculated. The accuracy of this calculation would be determined by the magnitude of the capacitive charge of the PANI film, the presence of side reactions between the redox active film M and the electrolyte $t^{composition}$ (i.e., transfer of anions from the electrolyte to the PANI film), and the diffusional period. As illustrated in Fig. 7c and Fig. S16, the thinner the aqueous phase is, the shorter the diffusional period and the closer the resemblance between pH-coulograms and volumetric titration curves.

5. Conclusions

The electrochemical release of ions from a redox active film to aqueous samples has been successfully rationalized via a mathematical model that considers charge transfer kinetics and 1D diffusion. Two coupled charge transfer events were considered: electron transfer between redox active film and a conductive substrate (ET), and an ion transfer from the film to the aqueous phase (IT). Advantageously, by invoking electroneutrality conditions in the film, the rate constant for the overall charge transfer (ET–IT) reaction could be described in terms of the overpotential for each step, and the model was simplified to consider only the IT event. The good agreement between the simulated and experimental results for H^+ release showed the validity of this approach, which significantly facilitates the analysis of complex systems in which redox- and ion-transfer processes are coupled (such as thin films of conducting polymers). In addition, the model predicts the effect of the thickness of the film and aqueous sample in the diffusional mass transport of the released ion, showing that in cases where the aqueous phase is confined to 100 μm (or thinner spatial domains), acidification with the ion pump produces pH-coulograms that bear a significant resemblance with classical volumetric titration curves.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Andres F. Molina-Osorio: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Formal analysis, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Alexander Wiorek:** Methodology, Investigation, Writing – original draft. **Ghulam Hussain:** Methodology, Investigation. **Maria Cuartero:** Conceptualization, Formal analysis, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition. **Gaston A. Crespo:** Conceptualization, Formal analysis, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jelechem.2021.115851>.

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